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POA ACTIONS IN SME-SP PUBLICATIONS IN THE YEARS 2018 AND 2019

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ABSTRACT

The educational public policy Professor Orientador de Área (POA) was instituted by Normative Instruction SME nº 25, of December 11, 2018, in Elementary School of the Municipal Education Network of the City of São Paulo, to contribute to the implementation of the new Curriculum of the City of São Paulo and, based on this, monitoring the planning of actions by the professionals involved. The general objective of this research was to analyze whether the legal apparatus determined by the respective Municipal Department of Education favored the performance of the function. To this end, in a qualitative approach, a documentary and descriptive research was developed, which considered the context of reality and the variables relevant to the investigation, through a State of the Art and Content Analysis. In view of the analysis of the normative acts involved in the implementation of the POA public policy, it was verified that there was a legal guarantee in the dimension of the participation of the professional designated for the function in the training and his performance with the peers, in the collective schedules of teaching study to deepen didactic-pedagogical studies, improve practices and implement them in guaranteeing student learning. This public policy is undoubtedly innovative and relevant, although the size of RME-SP demands complex and specific logistics.

Keywords: education; educational public policy; curriculum; teacher training; area guidance professor.

INTRODUCTION

The educational public policy Professor Orientador de Área (POA) was instituted by Normative Instruction SME nº 25, of December 11, 2018, in Elementary School of the Municipal Education Network of the City of São Paulo, to contribute to the implementation of the new Curriculum of the City of São Paulo and, based on this, in monitoring the planning of actions by the professionals involved. The POA constitutes the function destined to the effective teacher in the area of his attribution - Portuguese Language (Interdisciplinary and Authorial Cycles), Mathematics (Interdisciplinary and Authorial Cycles) or Teacher of Early Childhood Education and Elementary School I (PEIEF-I: Literacy Cycle) (SÃO PAULO, 2018b).

Considering this determination, the present research sought to identify whether the normative acts published by SME-SP, specifically regarding the POA public policy, favored the performance of the designated professor's function and, given the lack of definition of the profiles to characterize this recent task, it was decided to carry out a survey of the context in which it was cited in the digital public archives of the SME-SP during the period 2018 and 2019. That is, a parallel was built between the ideal identified in Articles 3, 4 and 17 of IN SME nº 25/2018, as well as in institutional guidance publications, and under the conditions determined in subsequent normative acts. In this perspective, Content Analysis techniques (BARDIN, 2016) were used, aiming to understand the manifest and latent discourse identified, as a result of verifying the presence, absence and frequency of the registration units that make up the categories coded from the scanned documents.

DEVELOPMENT

The research began by identifying registration units in Articles 3, 4 and 17 of IN SME No. 25/2018, which address the function, objectives and specific attributions of the POA. Having carried out the State of the Art of the theme through documentary research in strictly written and primary, contemporary and retrospective sources (LAKATOS; MARCONI, 2018a), data collection techniques were applied, which enabled

the elaboration of the mental map (Figure 1) which provided the first foundations for the creation of the research project.

Figure 1 – Pre-analysis : Mind map

Source: Prepared by the author (2019).

A first hypothesis (that the POA would allow the improvement of teachers' actions, from a perspective of integral, inclusive and equitable education) required an initial immersion in IN SME nº 25/2018 to identify the registration units and possible categories of analysis aligned with the objectives and attributions of the role, along with excerpts from this document. After further reading this Instruction, as well as gathering the other materials that make up the corpus, it was verified the need to focus on the registration units identified in Articles 3, 4 and 17, grouped into categories relevant to the research.

Finally, to distinguish the specific actions of the POA (mentioned in the publications of the SME-SP) we returned to the treatment of the material gathered with the Study of Art engaged in digital public archives, namely: portals of the Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo, the São Paulo City Department of Education, the Union of Education Specialists in Public Education in São Paulo and the Open Data Portals and Municipal Legislation.

The material was prepared in a word processor for better viewing and detection of terms through the Navigation Panel, highlighting the header and closing of each normative act, eliminating unnecessary numbering markers and adapting the font color.

After being saved in a word processor and having

detected (via the Navigation Panel) the pertinent citations, the 44 (forty-four) files – each arranged in tables containing a description and clipping – were grouped in folders, firstly according to the year of publication (2018 and 2019) and the discursive genre institutional guidelines and normative acts. The latter, given the diversity of purposes, were later grouped into POA-specific communications, non-POA-specific communications, registration opening communications, homologation dispatch, ordinances and normative instructions published in 2018 and 2019.

In this research, the variables are the categories constituted by the aspects that best characterize the POA public policy, using significant topics as a selection criterion for these aspects, that is, registration units present in Articles 3, 4 and 17 of IN SME n° 25/2018, which address the role, objectives and specific attributions of the POA.

In that section, the registration units were selected and, after studying and analyzing these terms in the other documents that make up the research corpus, there was a need to group them into 3 (three) categories, as shown in Chart 1, according to criterion of the topics that cover the respective registration units in the referred Articles: public policy, objectives and specific attributions.

Table 1 - Registration units and categories for analysis

Registration Units	Categories
Area Guiding Professor - POA (act) together with the Pedagogical Coordinator	Public policy
Implementation of the Curriculum of the City of São Paulo	
collaborate in the implementation of the Educational Policy	
contribute to the improvement of IDEB indexes	Goals
favor the development of a Political-Pedagogical Project	
(auxiliary) integration of the different Knowledge Areas	
constantly improve actions, based on the City's Curriculum	
participate in the planning of the didactic action together with the teachers	Specific Assignments
prepare annual work plan	
record [...] the pedagogical documentation accompanying the teaching planning	
Identify inconsistencies in the development of teaching and learning processes and propose interventions	

Source: Prepared by the author (2021)

Subsequently, the search for the terms POA and Professor Orientador de Área (both simultaneously) in the Google Scholar database and in public digital archives – portals of the Official Gazette of the

City of São Paulo, the Municipal Department of Education, the Union of Specialists in São Paulo Municipal Public School Education (SINESP) and the Open Data and Municipal Legislation Portals – showed that the research was unprecedented and there was a sufficient number of documents to carry out the State of the Art on the subject.

The use of the word processor, as well as its Navigation Panel, enabled the data collection process aimed at selecting and counting the recording units and their categories, making it possible to detect the presence, absence and frequency of variables in the documents. The charts were built with this same tool, but the figures and schemes were created in the program for creating/editing and displaying graphic presentations. During this process, notes and comments on the selected data were attached to the documents and the analysis of the selected information (especially in relation to Sobral's experience) required the search for other documents and data collection on the portals of DIEESE, OXFAM, IDEB, QEdU and IBEGE.

The spreadsheet editor was used to organize the data and process the information, with a view to discussing and analyzing the results and preparing the report.

Successive normative acts guided the actions of the implementation of this public policy, investing it with intentionality, attributions and specific training – represented in the summary presented in the Tables below.

At the end of 2018, there were the initial normative acts for the implementation of the POA, which make up Group 1 of analysis, present in Table 2.

Table 2 - Group 1: Normative Acts published in DO.online - Year 2018

Normative Acts published in DO.online - Year 2018	Categories
IN SME n° 22, 12/11/2018: Provides for the organization of early childhood education units, elementary education, elementary and secondary education and unified educational centers of the municipal education network for the year 2019, and other measures.	Public policy
IN SME No. 25, 12/11/2018: Provides for the organization of the complementary pedagogical support project - recovery, as well as the appointment of teachers to exercise the functions of pedagogical support	Public policy Goals

teacher - PAP and Area Advisor Professor - POA and make other arrangements	Assignments
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Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

At specific moments of the semesters, SME-SP published guiding institutional documents, in which the role of the POA was mentioned, as shown in Table 3, constituting Group 2 for analysis.

Table 3 – Group 2: Institutional Guidance Publications

Institutional Guidance Publications available on the SME-SP Portal	Categories
THE CURRICULUM OF THE CITY OF SÃO PAULO: An experience of updating and implementing curriculum for Elementary School based on the BNCC	Public policy Assignments
School Organization Meeting 2019 DRES / UEs	Public policy
Guidelines for Educational Units: 2nd semester - 2019	Public policy Assignments
Guiding document for the Portuguese language survey: Literacy Cycle - Elementary School	Assignments

Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

Analysis Group 3 is composed of the successive normative acts published during the year 2019. Due to its quantity and diversity of purposes, it was subdivided into 5 (five) groupings.

Table 4 lists the call notices to fill the POA vacancy in the mentioned EU.

Table 4 – GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online – Year 2018: Registration open

Normative acts published in DO.online – Year 2019: registration opening	Categories
COMMUNICATE NO. 35 OF APRIL 4, 2019 04/06/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - Pag. 52 DRE CAMPO LIMPO	Public policy
COMMUNICATE No. 20, 04/22/2019 04/26/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - Pag. 93 DIRECTOR OF GUAIANASES	Public policy
COMMUNICATION No. 72 of 11/26/2019 11/28/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - Pag. 48 DRE CAMPO LIMPO	Public policy
COMMUNICATION No. 42 OF 12/05/2019 12/07/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - Pag. 34 DRE PIRITUBA/JARAGUÁ	Public policy
COMMUNICATE NO. 73 OF DECEMBER 2019 12/14/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - Pag. 56 DRE SÃO MIGUEL	Public policy

Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

Table 5 contains the announcements of continuing teacher training courses specific to the POA, to be taught by the SME-SP team of trainers.

Table 5 - GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online – Year 2018: Specific announcements to POA

Normative acts published in DO.online – Year 2018: Specific notices to POA	Categories
COMMUNICATE No. 243, OF 03/27/2019. Making the publication in the DO.online of 04/09/2019, page 42	Public policy Goals
03/28/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 36 COMMUNICATE No. 243 OF MARCH 27, 2019. Promoter area: SME/COPED/DIEFEM Made void with publication No. 313, of April 17, 2019.	Public policy Goals
04/18/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - page 41 COMMUNICATE No. 313, OF APRIL 17, 2019. Promoter area: DIEFEM Making the publication in the DO.online of 03/28/2019, PAGE. 36 Rectified by the publication of the DO.online of 04/18/2019 - page 41 COMMUNICATE NO. 313 OF APRIL 17, 2019.	Public policy Goals
08/27/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 37 Education. Secretary's Office Rectification of the DO.online publication of 04/18/2019 – page 41 COMMUNICATE No. 313, OF APRIL 17, 2019.	Public policy Goals
04/12/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 42 COMMUNICATE No. 295, OF APRIL 11, 2019. Promoter area: SME / COPED / DIEFEM	Public policy Goals
04/12/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 42 COMMUNICATE No. 295, OF APRIL 11, 2019. Promoter area: SME / COPED / DIEFEM Corrected by the publication of communiqué n° 295, of April 11, 2019.	Public policy Goals
08/16/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - Pag. 37 Rectification of the DO.online publication of 04/12/2019 – page 42. COMMUNICATE No. 295, OF APRIL 11, 2019.	Public policy Goals
Rectification of publication of DO.online of 08/14/2019 - page 42 COMMUNICATION No. 608, OF AUGUST 13, 2019.	Public policy Goals
08/20/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 33 COMMUNICATION No. 624, OF AUGUST 19, 2019. Promoter area: COPED/DIEFEM	Public policy Goals
08/14/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - page 42 Education. Secretary's Office COMMUNICATE No. 608 OF AUGUST 13, 2019. Promoter area: COPED/DIEFEM Corrected by the publication of communiqué n° 608, of August 13, 2019.	Public policy Goals

(to be continued)
(conclusion)

Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

Table 6 contains the announcements of continuing teacher training courses that are not exclusive to teachers assigned to the role of POA, but specific to this public policy.

Table 6 - GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online – Year 2018: Announcements not specific to POA

GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online - Year 2018: Announcements not specific to POA	Categories
07/30/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 37 COMMUNICATION No. 554 OF JULY 29, 2019. Promoter area: COPED/DIEFEM	Public policy Goals
05/15/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 47 COMMUNICATE No. 385 OF MAY 14, 2019 Promoter area: ELEMENTARY AND HIGH SCHOOL EDUCATION DIVISION	Public policy Goals
07/12/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 48 COMMUNICATION No. 507, OF JULY 11, 2019. Promoter areas: COPED/DIEFEM/UNICEU	Public policy Goals
07/17/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 32 COMMUNICATE No. 39, OF APRIL 12, 2019. Promoter area: DRE CAMPO LIMPO	Public policy Goals
07/26/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 34 COMMUNICATE No. 36, JULY 23, 2019. Promoter area: DRE/DIPED ITAQUERA	Public policy Goals
08/20/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 34 COMMUNICATE No. 36, OF AUGUST 14, 2019 Promoter area: DIPED IPIRANGA .	Public policy Goals
08/28/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 33 COMMUNICATION No. 648, OF AUGUST 27, 2019 Promoter area: COPED/DIEFEM .	Public policy Goals
11/19/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - page 47 COMMUNICATE No. 823, OF NOVEMBER 18, 2019. Promoter area: DIEFEM	Public policy Goals

Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

In Table 7, there is the approval of the course prepared by Sindsep , aimed at professionals affiliated to this union, including those designated as POA, therefore, not specific to this.

Table 7 - GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online - Year 2018: Approval order

GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online - Year 2018: Approval order	Categories
08/29/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - Pag. 47 Education. Secretary's Office Approval Order No. 19378 COURSE: Considerations on the Curriculum of the City: Early Childhood Education	Goals

Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

The ordinances, listed in Table 8, deal with the authorization of the waiver of a point at the time coinciding with the event, safeguarding the time for locomotion, for teachers who participate in training courses specific to the work of the POA, that is, the time of moving around and staying on the course was considered a day worked.

Table 8 - GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online - Year 2018: Ordinances

GROUP 3: Normative acts published in DO.online - Year 2019: Ordinances	Categories
04/18/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - page 19 ORDINANCE No. 3.791, OF APRIL 17, 2019	Public policy
ORDINANCE No. 3.792, OF APRIL 17, 2019	Public policy
ORDINANCE No. 3.793, OF APRIL 17, 2019	Public policy
07/30/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 16 Education. Secretary's Office ORDINANCE No. 5.950, OF JULY 29, 2019	Public policy
08/14/2019 - Official Gazette City of São Paulo - page 19 ORDINANCE No. 6,364, OF AUGUST 13, 2019	Public policy
08/20/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 14 Education. Secretary's Office ORDINANCE No. 6.553, OF AUGUST 19, 2019	Public policy
08/24/2019 - Official Gazette of the City of São Paulo - page 17 Education. Secretary's Office ORDINANCE No. 6.686, OF AUGUST 22, 2019	Public policy

Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

Chart 9 is composed of Analysis Group 4, where the Normative Instructions published in 2019 are gathered, with a view to improving the implementation of the POA public policy.

Table 9 - GROUP 4: Normative acts published in DO.online - Year 2019

GROUP 4: Normative acts published in DO.online - Year 2019	Categories
NORMATIVE INSTRUCTION SME No. 14, OF JUNE 5, 2019 Amends Normative Instruction No. 25, of 12/11/18, provides for the organization of the Complementary Pedagogical Support Project - Recovery, as well as for the appointment of teachers to exercise the functions of Pedagogical Support Professor - PAP and Area Guiding Professor - POA and other provisions.	Public policy Goals
NORMATIVE INSTRUCTION SME No. 31 OF OCTOBER 31, 2019 Deals with the reorganization of the function of the Area Guiding Professor - POA, and other measures.	Public policy Goals Assignments
NORMATIVE INSTRUCTION SME No. 40, 11/29/2019 Deals with the Initial Process of Choosing/Assigning Shifts and Classes/Blocks/Classes to Teachers of the Municipal Education Network - RME, who work in Municipal Child Education Centers - CEMEIs, Municipal Infant Education Schools - EMEIs , Municipal Schools of Elementary Education - EMEFs, Municipal Elementary and Secondary Education Schools, Municipal Bilingual Education Schools for the Deaf - EMEBSs, Municipal Elementary and Secondary Education Schools - EMEFMs and Integrated Youth and Adult Education Centers - CIEJAs and other measures.	Public policy
NORMATIVE INSTRUCTION SME No. 45, OF DECEMBER 11, 2019 Provides for the organization of early childhood education units, elementary education, primary and secondary education and unified educational centers of the municipal education network for the year 2020, and makes other provisions.	Public policy

Source: Prepared by the Author (2021).

CONCLUSION

It was found that in the various documents directed to the POA, the function is continually mentioned associated with its specificity in contributing to the implementation of the Curriculum of the City of São Paulo, giving credibility to its actions. Emphasis is identified on the delimitation of certain times for the deepening of studies and reflection on practices, essentially with their peers, an essential routine. Acting as a teaching partner of CP, the POA has access to differentiated training that accredits him/her to encourage the teaching team to:

- Strengthen the implementation of the City Curriculum;
- Understand the concept of literacy present in the City's Curriculum;
- Reflect on the didactic work as an object of knowledge and on the text as an object of teaching;
- Reflect on pedagogical strategies;
- Identify organizational modalities in a pedagogical routine;
- Analyze didactic situations and sequences of activities and case studies.
- Reflect on the different ways of organizing the room to encourage exchange and construction of knowledge;
- Share experiences;
- Analyze students' productions, with a view to teacher interaction and intervention;
- Adapt and take advantage of available resources;
- Participate in the territory's educational community.

However, the performance of the POA has as a parameter its continuous alignment with the CP, when studying the theoretical and methodological assumptions of the City's Curriculum in order to subsidize the work of the POA; reflect on strategies for monitoring learning and relating them to the importance of the teaching lesson plan, as well as the characteristics that need to be present in teaching practices in the classroom; promote Professional Reading to deepen knowledge and Professional Writing to problematize the difficulties experienced; and to critically analyze POA practices to support the planning of didactic action together

with the professors of the component that it holds and with the CP.

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